

Supplementary material

3D printing of a multi-performative facade

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Outlook of the project

This supplementary material is an annex to a study on the feasibility of mono-material extrusion for a multi-performative facade prototype. A facade element was designed and manufactured measuring 1.6 x 2 meters with integrating fabrication and environmental performances in the facade geometry see *Figure 1*. The fabricated elements were evaluated in a facade test rig for air permeability, water tightness,

resistance to wind loads, and impact resistance. The facade passed serviceability and safety for resistance to wind loads as well as maximum class for impact strength. These results proved that multi-performative additive manufactured facades could be manufactured in a mono-material geometry.

Figure 1. Additive manufactured facade panel (left picture) placed in a façade test rig (right picture)

Content

This document is to support the study claim with additional experiments, drawings, and calculations. It contains the following sections:

1. Connection tests
2. Brackets
3. Metal brackets
4. Wind loads

1. Connection tests

This section details the design and testing of the initial iterations for the facade connections, see *Figure 2a*. Vertical and horizontal connections were tested for three-point flexural testing to identify which printing direction of the toolpath has a better mechanical strength, see *Figure 2b*.

a

b

Figure 2. a) Example of facade panel connections for vertical and horizontal direction with gaskets, b) Three-point flexural testing setup for the connection mechanical strength.

The printing direction was essential in the design and manufacturing step, to identify how to 3D print the facade panel, see *Figure 3*. For this reason, 2 prototypes of 4 connection for vertical direction and 2 prototypes of 4 connections for the horizontal direction were manufactured, see *Figure 4*. The testing results proved that **horizontal** printing direction has better structural strength of $F_{\max}^1 = 3870$ and $F_{\max}^2 = 5070$ N, compared to the vertical printing direction which reached $F_{\max}^1 = 2950$ and $F_{\max}^2 = 2300$ N, see *Figure 5*.

Figure 3. Horizontal and vertical printing direction of the connection¹

¹ I. Cheibas, R. P. Gamote, B. Önalán, E. Lloret-Fritschí, F. Gramazio, and M. Kohler, “Additive Manufactured (3D-Printed) Connections for Thermoplastic Facades,” in *Trends on Construction in the Digital Era*, 2023, pp. 145–166.

b

Figure 4. a) Prototype fabricated with horizontal printing direction, comprised of 2 snap-fit connections; b) Prototype fabricated with vertical printing direction, comprised of 2 snap-fit connections.

a

b

Figure 5. The four prototypes breaking in three point flexural tests with maximum load applied of a) 2950 N and b) 5070 N.

2. Brackets

This section details the calculations required for the bracket design of the back surface in the facade panels. These brackets are essential for a reliant structural strength in the facade connection to the building structure.

a

b

c

Figure 6. a) Design sketch of the bracket connection to a building structure; b) 3D model of the bracket connection to the structure; c) Sample designated for structural testing of the final design and position of the brackets on the façade panels.

The following calculations were performed to identify the brackets performance in response to load transmission of the facade elements.

7 Aug 2023 13:30:12 - Calculation Brackets_test 1.sm

Digital Fabrication: 1122163-00

Loads

$P_v := 1.5 \text{ kPa}$ Wind Load
 $\gamma_Q := 1.5$ $\gamma_G := 1.35$

Geometry

$B_m := 1.8 \text{ m}$
 $H_m := 3.5 \text{ m}$
 $A_m := B_m \cdot H_m = 6.3 \text{ m}^2$

Dead Load- (H) (solides unit) 40% macizo

$\rho := 1.23 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$ "PETG"
 $t_m := 150 \text{ mm}$ panel de 150 mm de espesor

$M := 0.4 \cdot \rho \cdot t_m \cdot B_m \cdot H_m = 464.94 \text{ kg}$ Max. Dead Load

Bracket geometry

$d_s := 20 \text{ mm}$
 $r_1 := 10 \text{ mm}$ Regulation: the most onerous position
 $L_1 := 30 \text{ mm}$

Material

$f_y := 15 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$ No en todas las direcciones!!!. Ver ensayos
 $\gamma_M := 2$ Per DIN 18516 - chapter 6.4.3

$E := 1480 \text{ MPa}$

$t_k := 10 \text{ mm}$ thickness material

$F := P_v \cdot \frac{A_m}{2} = 4725 \text{ N}$

Section 1

$d_{br_max} := L_1 - \left(\frac{d_s - r_1}{2} \right) = 25 \text{ mm}$

$t_1 := 30 \text{ mm}$

$H_b := 150 \text{ mm}$

$A_{s1} := 2 \cdot ((H_b - t_k) + (t_1 - t_k)) \cdot t_k = 3200 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_{x_s1} := 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{12} \cdot (t_1) \cdot t_k^3 + t_1 \cdot t_k \cdot \left(\frac{H_b - t_k}{2} \right)^2 \right) + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \cdot t_k \cdot (H_b - 2 \cdot t_k)^3 = 660.6667 \text{ cm}^4$

$W_{x_s1} := \frac{I_{x_s1}}{\frac{H_b}{2}} = 88.0889 \text{ cm}^3$

$Med_{s1} := \gamma_Q \cdot F \cdot d_{br_max} = 1.7719 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N mm}$

$\sigma_{vm_s1} := \sqrt{\left(\frac{Med_{s1}}{W_{x_s1}} \right)^2 + 3 \cdot \left(\frac{F}{A_{s1}} \right)^2} = 3.2537 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$

$\sigma_{vm_s1} < \frac{f_y}{\gamma_M} = 26.5 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$

$\% \text{ Use} := \frac{\sigma_{vm_s1}}{\frac{f_y}{\gamma_M}} \cdot 100 = 43.3829$

Section 2

$$dbr2_max := \left(\frac{ds - r1}{2} + 25 \text{ mm} \right) = 30 \text{ mm}$$

$$t2 := 28 \text{ mm}$$

$$As2 := 2 \cdot \left((Hb - tk) + (t2 - tk) \right) \cdot tk = 3160 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$Ix_s2 := 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{12} \cdot (t2) \cdot tk^3 + t2 \cdot tk \cdot \left(\frac{Hb - tk}{2} \right)^2 \right) + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \cdot tk \cdot (Hb - 2 \cdot tk)^3 = 641.0333 \text{ cm}^4$$

$$Wx_s2 := \frac{Ix_s2}{\frac{Hb}{2}} = 85.4711 \text{ cm}^3$$

$$Med_s2 := \gamma Q \cdot F \cdot dbr2_max = 2.1263 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N mm}$$

$$\sigma_{vm_s2} := \sqrt{\left(\frac{Med_s2}{Wx_s2} \right)^2 + 3 \cdot \left(\frac{F}{As2} \right)^2} = 3.5911 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$$

$$\sigma_{vm_s2} < \frac{fy}{\gamma M} = 26.5 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$$

$$\% \text{ Use} := \frac{\sigma_{vm_s2}}{\frac{fy}{\gamma M}} \cdot 100 = 47.8812$$

Section 3

$$dbr3_max := \left(\frac{ds - r1}{2} + 52.5 \text{ mm} \right) = 57.5 \text{ mm}$$

$$t3 := 65 \text{ mm}$$

$$As3 := 2 \cdot \left((Hb - tk) + (t3 - tk) \right) \cdot tk = 3900 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$Iy_s3 := 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{12} \cdot (Hb) \cdot tk^3 + Hb \cdot tk \cdot \left(\frac{t3 - tk}{2} \right)^2 \right) + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \cdot tk \cdot (t3 - 2 \cdot tk)^3 = 244.5625 \text{ cm}^4$$

$$Wy_s3 := \frac{Iy_s3}{\frac{t3}{2}} = 75.25 \text{ cm}^3$$

$$Ix_s3 := 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{12} \cdot (t3) \cdot tk^3 + t3 \cdot tk \cdot \left(\frac{Hb - tk}{2} \right)^2 \right) + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \cdot tk \cdot (Hb - 2 \cdot tk)^3 = 1004.25 \text{ cm}^4$$

$$Wx_s3 := \frac{Ix_s3}{\frac{Hb}{2}} = 133.9 \text{ cm}^3$$

Wind Load

$$Medy_s3 := \gamma Q \cdot F \cdot dbr3_max = 4.0753 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N mm}$$

Dead Load

$$Medx_s3 := \gamma G \cdot \frac{M}{2} \cdot 9.81 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} \cdot 29 \text{ mm} = 89282.7769 \text{ N mm}$$

$$\sigma_{vm_s3} := \sqrt{\left(\frac{Medy_s3}{Wy_s3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{Medx_s3}{Wx_s3} \right)^2 + 3 \cdot \left(\frac{F}{As3} \right)^2} = 5.8462 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$$

$$\sigma_{vm_s3} < \frac{fy}{\gamma M} = 26.5 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$$

$$\% \text{ Use} := \frac{\sigma_{vm_s3}}{\frac{fy}{\gamma M}} \cdot 100 = 77.9491$$

a
b
Figure 7. a) 3D printed sample with PETG to test the load transmission of the bracket; b) Samples tested for load transmission.

3. Metal brackets

This section details the calculations and design specifications required for the metal brackets. These brackets are made of steel and are very important for correct functioning of the facade. When testing a facade, the brackets are also part of the tested facade system. Thanks to the three-axis adjustment, correct positioning is possible. In order to cope with the manufacturing tolerances of the panel, a bespoke anchorage has been designed with adjustment screws for fine adjustment. This allows the panel to be positioned and to allow for expansion within the manufacturing and assembly tolerances. The structural dimensioning of the loads was done by means of finite element calculations, see Figure .

Figure 8. Metal brackets design in front, side, and isometric view displaying the potential of a flexible adjustment of the facade brackets to the building structure.

Figure 9. Finite analysis method to identify the metal brackets response to structural loads.

4. Wind loads

This section details the calculations required for the wind loads design of the PETG façade element. These calculation conclude that for a panel 1.8 m wide and 3.5 m height, the material works at 78% of its use for a 1.5 kPa design wind load. This wind load is estimated from calculations made for a facade in a Zurich building with dimensions of 15 m × 20 m × 40 m, according to the SIA 261 standard:

Date:
 Work: ETH

Largeur/ Länge: d = 50 m
 Profondeur/ Breite: b = 20 m
 Hauteur / Höhe des Bauteils: (h) z = 40 m

Valeur de référence de la pression dynamique /
 Referenz Staudruck: $q_{p0} = 0.9 \text{ kN/m}^2$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.3 (Annexe/ Anhang E)
 Catégorie de terrain / Geländekategorie: $Z > 30 = III$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.2 (Tableau 4)
 Gradientenhöhe: $z_g = 450 \text{ m}$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.2 (Tableau 4)
 Bodenrauigkeit: $\alpha_r = 0.23$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.2 (Tableau 4)
 Coefficient du profil de répartition/ Profilbeiwert: $c_h = 1.44$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.2

Pression dynamique / Staudruck $q_p = 1.294423 \text{ kN/m}^2$ SIA 261:2020_6.2.1.1 (11)

h:b:d = 2:2.5:1 => Tableau 38

Coefficients de pression extérieure: "o Werte": Ungünstige Sogmessung an der Gebäudekante

0°	$C_{p,e} = -0.9$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)
15°	$C_{p,e} = -1.1$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)
45°	$C_{p,e} = -0.6$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)
90°	$C_{p,e} = -0.55$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)
Druck +	$C_{p,e} = 0.8$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)

Coefficients de pression intérieure:

	$C_{p,i} = 0$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)
	$C_{p,i} = -0.4$	SIA 261:2020 (Annexe C - Tabelle 38)

Coefficients totaux de pression:

0°	$C_{p,net} = -0.9$
15°	$C_{p,net} = -1.1$
45°	$C_{p,net} = -0.6$
90°	$C_{p,net} = -0.55$
Druck +	$C_{p,net} = 1.2$

Wind Lasten am Ecke!:

0°	Wo = -1164.98 Pa	d/10 (m) = 5.00
15°	Wo = -1423.87 Pa	
45°	Wo = -776.654 Pa	
90°	Wo = -711.933 Pa	
Druck +	Wo = 1553.308 Pa	

Tabelle 38 Beiwerte für $h : b : d = 2 : 2,5 : 1$, Dachneigung 30°

φ	Lokale Druckbeiwerte															Globale Kraftbeiwerte			
	C_{pe}								C_{pe}			C_{pi}				C_{F1}	C_{F2}	C_{F3}	
	Teilfläche								Teilfläche			Undichtheit vorherrschend auf Fläche				Bezugsfläche			
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	m	n	o	glm.	A	B	C	D	$b \cdot h$	$0,93 \cdot d \cdot h$	$d \cdot b$
0°	0,8	-0,6	-0,95	-0,95	-0,45	-0,45	-0,55	-0,55	-0,65	-0,65	-0,9	-0,4	0,8	-0,65	-0,9	-0,9	1,21	0	-0,5
15°	0,6	-0,55	-0,65	-0,75	-0,25	-0,45	-0,55	-0,65	-0,65	-0,65	-1,1	-0,3	0,6	-0,55	-0,85	-0,75	1,02	0,1	-0,48
45°	0,4	-0,55	0,4	-0,6	-0,3	-0,4	-0,8	-0,7	-0,6	-0,75	-0,6	0,1	0,4	-0,55	0,35	-0,6	0,87	1,0	-0,55
90°	-0,6	-0,6	0,85	-0,25	-0,8	-0,3	-0,8	-0,3	-1,1	-1,1	-0,55	-0,15	-0,55	-0,55	0,85	-0,25	0	1,1	-0,55
	$\hat{C}_{pe} = -2,0$															$C_{F3} = 0$			

Figur 6 Profilbeiwert c_p in Abhängigkeit von der Höhe z für die Geländekategorien II, IIa, III und IV

Tabelle 4 Gradientenhöhe z_g und Exponent der Bodenrauigkeit α_r

Geländekategorie	Beispiele	z_g in m	α_r
II	Seeufer	300	0,16
IIa	grosse Ebene	380	0,19
III	Ortschaften, freies Feld	450	0,23
IV	grossflächige Stadtgebiete	526	0,30

o: ungünstigste Sogmessung an der Gebäudekante

Anhang
Annexe
Appendice
Annex

E
Referenzwert des Staudrucks
Valeur référence de la pression dynamique
Valore di riferimento della pressione dinamica
Reference value of the dynamic pressure

Additionally a thermal dilation was measured to identify the facade panels movement during testing.

Calculation thermal dilatation			
$\Delta l = l_0 \cdot \alpha \cdot \Delta t$	Tfab	=	20 °C
	Tmin	=	-10 °C
	Tmax	=	50 °C
	ΔT	=	30 °C
Thermal dilatation coeficient	α	=	0.00006 m/m °C
Length initial vertical	L0V	=	3500 mm
Length initial horizontal	L0H	=	2000 mm
	ΔLvertical	=	6.3 mm
	ΔLHorizontal	=	3.6 mm

Fabrication & Instalation tolerances			
	+/- ΔTol fab	=	2 mm
	+/- ΔTol inst	=	2 mm

Main Structure movement-Vertical			
	+/- ΔMStructur	=	3 mm

	ΔLvertical	=	9.9 mm
Total max movement	ΔLHorizontal	=	6.4 mm